

Thulium-doped fiber laser with longitudinally segmented active fiber

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays, one of the main challenges of thulium-doped fiber lasers is thermal management. One prospective method to significantly reduce thermal load density along the fiber is using a segmented active fiber or active fiber with a longitudinal gradient of thulium-doping concentration. Based on a theoretical model, the laser design with a segmented active fiber was proposed and initial measurements and tests were done. It was achieved 30 W of stable output power at 1940 nm with a launched slope efficiency exceeding 60 %, and better heat distribution along the fiber than in uniformly doped lasers.

Keywords: fiber laser, thulium, inhomogeneous concentration

1. INTRODUCTION

Two-micron sources of radiation are in high demand for their widespread utilization in areas such as defence [1], industrial [2], or biomedical [3] applications. Thulium-doped fiber lasers (TDFLs) offer access to a wide emission spectral range in this region and take advantage of the so-called two-for-one cross-relaxation process leading up to the theoretical doubling of the overall quantum efficiency up to 2 [4]. Nowadays, one of the main challenges is thermal management, as the active fiber core can reach up to 300 °C during the laser operation, but power scaling is hindered by the much lower temperature limit of the polymer outer-coating around 80 °C [5].

Various strategies have been explored to overcome overheating in TDFLs. One approach involves an in-band pumping scheme, where the fiber is pumped at around 1610-1710 nm, thereby reducing the quantum defect and the associated heat load [6]. The main present drawback is low-efficient laser diodes on these wavelengths or the need for a more complex system, including tandem pumping [7]. Another approach is advanced fiber fabrication techniques optimizing the concentration and distribution of thulium ions (Tm^{3+}) within the fiber, such as structured or segmented-core fiber designs [8]. Additionally, the development of advanced cooling techniques, such as applying metal coatings [9], can further enhance heat dissipation.

A prospective method to significantly reduce thermal load density along the fiber is also using a segmented active fiber or active fiber with a longitudinal gradient of thulium-doping concentration. These fibers would benefit from lower concentration of Tm^{3+} at the beginning of an active fiber where significant heat load can be expected due to high pump absorption, and high concentration towards the far end of the fiber, enabling an efficient two-for-one cross-relaxation process [10].

2. EXPERIMENT

The experiment was conducted using in-house fabricated thulium-doped pedestal fiber with the core, pedestal, and cladding (flat to flat) dimensions of 12, 31, and 132 μm , respectively. This fiber showed a longitudinal inhomogeneous thulium concentration, which enabled maintaining a minimal variation in the mode field diameter when using different sections. In the experiment, three different segments were used with a Tm^{3+} concentration of 6900 (fiber A), 13700 (fiber B), and

Figure 1. Experimental setup with depicted configurations of segmented fibers.

16000 (fiber C) molar ppm. The concentration was derived from cladding absorption measurement and fiber dimensions. Firstly, individual segments were measured in the laser setup shown in Figure 1. The pump was provided by a BWT laser diode (LD) at 792 nm, and Thorlabs FG105UCA fiber (Hi OH) was implemented to protect LD from 2 μm radiation. The resonator was formed by high reflectivity fiber Bragg grating (FBG), centred around 1940 nm (Teraxion), and by a Fresnel reflection on a perpendicularly cleaved end. A passive fiber Nufern SM-GDF served to minimize the mode-field diameter mismatch between the active fiber and the FBG. The residual pump power was filtered by a silicon filter. Using cut-back measurement, the maximal slope efficiency with respect to pump power was determined. According to the results, segmented active fibers were prepared and measured in the same setup. For the initial test, two lasers containing two segments with a similar doping concentration and fiber length were created (2-seg-uni and 2-seg). While the first one was uniformly doped fiber B containing one splice in the middle to reduce its influence, the second one consisted of fibers A and C. For further experiments active fiber containing all three segments was designed (3-seg). All arrangements are depicted in Figure 1.

3. RESULTS

The individual segments in the laser setup showed the optimum length in the range of 2.5-4 m with a slope efficiency of 58.2-66.2 % depending on the concentration. Particular values are summarized in Table 1.

Table 2. Slope efficiencies and optimal fiber lengths for individual segments.

Fiber label	A	B	C
Concentration (mol ppm)	6900	13700	16000
Fiber length (m)	4.0	3.0	3.0
Slope efficiency (%)	58.2	65.2	66.2

The slope efficiency of 2-seg TDFL was 56.6 %, higher than that of the uniformly doped 2-seg-uni by 3 %. Since these values are lower than for individual segments, it must be noted, that the length of the fibers was not optimized to keep a

Figure 2. Laser performance of 2-segmented TDFLs and the thermal camera images of (a) 2-seg and (b) 2-seg-uni under the pump power of ~16 W [11].

similar average concentration. The performance of both lasers is shown in Figure 2 as well as the thermal camera images under the same pump of ~16 W. The temperature label indicates the highest value in the marked area. The heat distribution along the 2-seg fiber was more even, allowing the fiber to handle higher pump powers. Consequently, the temperature of 2-seg-uni reached 110 °C just before the splice failure.

For better proof of this concept, a 3-seg laser was designed and optimized. As can be seen in Figure 3a, the laser reached a slope efficiency of 62.3 % with an output power of 30 W. The temperature measurement shown in Figure 3b indicates a notably improved heat distribution. It can be also observed that the splice between the first and second segment (peak between S1-S2) was warmer than the splice where the pump power enters the first segment of active fiber (the peak before S1), which suggests that the lengths and concentrations of the individual active fibers can be designed more effectively. Moreover, the measurement was compared with numerical simulations, where the temperature was calculated from heat load using the analytical model [5].

Figure 3. a) Laser performance of 3-seg TDFLs and b) comparison of simulated and measured temperature along the active fiber of 3-seg TDFL [11].

4. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we reported the laser design with a longitudinally segmented active fiber, and the initial measurements and tests were done. The results indicate that, compared to uniformly doped fibers, the heat load can be spread more evenly within the whole fiber length, enabling it to withstand higher pump powers. As this fiber was composed of several segments spliced together, the output laser characteristics are affected by these splices. This could be improved by using a single fiber with a concentration gradient, which is currently challenging to achieve due to the limitations of existing technology. Even though it was possible to reach up to 30 W of stable output power at 1940 nm and with launched slope efficiency exceeding 60 %.

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